

Thermal analysis in an agitated tank fitted with vertical HDPE radiators used as heat transfer surfaces

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Área de participación: Ingeniería mecánica

Abstract.

The aim of this research was to analyse the thermal performance of an agitated liquid tank, using as heat transfer surfaces four vertical plastic radiators type heaters made of high-density polyethylene, HDPE, in the form of in-line and staggered tube bundles. The system was tested using a range of water supplies rates between 2000 to 4000 l/h, at a rotation speed of 45, 60 and 100 rpm of the agitator within the tank. The experiments were run at an initial temperature of approximately 22°C and a final temperature of 40°C in the tank. The tank contained water which was heated by the HDPE heaters. The best heat transfer coefficient of 1470 W/m²K was obtained with the in-line tube bundle, at 4000 l/h flow of water and an agitator velocity of 100 rpm, and this was approximately 52% higher compared with the staggered tube bundle.

Keywords: Agitated tank, HDPE heaters, plastic compact heat exchanger, vertical tubes bundle.

Resumen

El propósito de esta investigación fue analizar el comportamiento térmico de un tanque de agitación utilizando como superficies de transferencia de calor 4 radiadores construidos con polietileno de alta densidad, HDPE. Los arreglos de los tubos fueron cuadrangular y triangular. El equipo fue investigado usando un intervalo de flujo de fluido de 2000 a 4000 l/h en los tubos a una velocidad de 100 rpm en el tanque. El trabajo experimental se inició cuando en el tanque se obtuvo una temperatura de aproximadamente 22°C y finalizó cuando se alcanzó una temperatura de 40°C. El fluido fue agua fría, la cual fue calentada con agua caliente que circulaba en los radiadores. El mejor resultado del coeficiente de transferencia de calor se obtuvo con el radiador con arreglo de tubo cuadrangular, siendo el flujo de fluido en el arreglo de tubos de 4000 l/h y la velocidad de 100 rpm en el tanque, este valor fue de 1470 W/m²K, aproximadamente 52% mayor que el obtenido con el arreglo triangular.

Palabras clave: Tanque de agitación, radiador construido con HPDE, intercambiador de calor compacto, arreglo de tubos verticales.

Introduction

In large agitated tanks it is necessary to use heat transfer surfaces inside the systems. The common heat transfer surfaces are jackets and helical, and these have been studied by Oldshue et al. and Ghotli R.A et al. [1-2]. The most widely heat transfer surfaces used in an agitated system is the jacket, where the heat is transferred through the vessel or tank wall. The jacket surface has the fewest variables to analyse and offers advantages related to the initial cost and operation economy. The main limitation is that the heat transfer surface is small for a given tank volume, and adjustment of the jacket area after the tank has been constructed is not possible. Large heat transfer surfaces can be obtained using helical heaters for a given volume of process fluid. However, the coils are generally more costly to construct and more difficult to maintain.

Vertical tube heat transfer surfaces are rarely used. A bank of heater tubes serves as a baffle as well as heat transfer surface. The baffles produce eddy currents in the liquid, which can improve the heat transfer process. On other hand, the baffles provide enough resistance to fluid motion to prevent any vortex formation and can generate large vertical and radial components of flow, which are desired for good mixing.

Petree and Small [3] used vertical plate coils, as a heat transfer surface, and one of the earliest studies of the heat transfer coefficient using vertical heater tube bundles in an agitated tank was carried out by Dunlap and Rushton [4]. The system consisted of a tank 1.22 m diameter and 1.525 m deep. A vertical tube bundle used as the heating area was located in the tank opposite to a vertical tube cooling bundle. In this study a correlation of the heat transfer coefficient for the agitated system was developed. Another work in the literature related to vertical tubes used as heat transfer surface was carried out by Havas et al. [5]. Here the heat transfer correlation developed by Dunlap and Rushton and the Reynolds number expression were modified. Experimental investigation was carried out in order to validate the modified correlation. According to the authors, the experimental data and values predicted using the modified correlations were in reasonable agreement within the range of the heat transfer coefficient used.

Dostál et al. [6] measured the heat transfer coefficients of heater tube baffles using the transient method, when the agitated liquid was periodically heated and cooled by the liquid running through the tube baffles. Solving the enthalpy balance, it was possible to determine the heat transfer coefficient. The results were summarized by the Nusselt number correlations, which describe the dependency on the Reynolds number, and they were compared with other measurements obtained by a steady-state method.

Rosa et al. [7] determined the parameters for the external coefficient of heat transfer in a tank fitted with vertical heater tube baffles, equipped with a turbine type radial-flow impeller with six flat-blade disk turbines. In this study, according to the authors, the predictions of the external coefficient of convection in a steady state flow were satisfactory. The use of a radial impeller in the heat transfer processes with vertical tube baffles resulted in greater heating efficiency compared to the axial impeller. In the publication of Fouad et al. [8] the vertical heater tube array served as a cooler or simultaneously as a cooler and a catalyst support for conducting exothermic diffusion controlled reactions. The mixing process used expensive materials to construct the heat transfer surfaces including steel alloys, galvanised iron alloys, copper-nickel alloys, and titanium. An alternative to reduce the cost of the surfaces for the mixing process was to use plastics. These materials offer the potential advantages of reduced cost and manufacture, resistance to corrosion and fouling, lower friction coefficients, reduced weight, and easy installation.

Some studies carried out by several researchers [9-15] reported that the plastic materials can be used to build industrial heat exchangers for process at low temperature and low pressure. Even though the results were not as good as with metals, their other properties make them competitive in building heat exchangers. The use of plastic for heat exchanger surfaces in applications involving corrosive materials at moderate temperatures has increased. Development of inexpensive plastic heat transfer surfaces for mixing process is a challenge because of the low thermal conductivity of the plastic and the temperature and pressure requirements in hot systems. The main limitation for heat transfer is the low thermal conductivity, which is lower than metals. To obtain reasonable heat transfer performance it is necessary to use very thin walled tubes which, in turn, means that they are only suitable for low pressure use. They can normally be used for heating or cooling fluids from -50°C to 150°C .

The aim of this research was to investigate the heat transfer coefficient on an agitated tank, fitted with vertical tube bundle heaters with in-line or staggered arrangements used as heat transfer surfaces, in order to select the most suitable type of heater for the agitated tank. All the tube bundles were made of high-density polyethylene, HDPE. In addition, corrosion resistance and fouling in the heaters were tested.

Overall Experimental Set up Rig

The main components of the overall experimental rig were the tank containing the HDPE heater and an agitator; the jacketed vessel, the circulation pump, temperature, and pressure measuring devices as it is shown in Fig. 1.

The two working fluids used in this system were hot water and cold water. The hot water was circulated through the heaters in order to heat the cold water in the tank. The hot water was maintained at a constant temperature by means of a jacketed vessel heated with steam. The hot water flowed from the jacketed vessel through a pump to provide sufficient driving force to circulate the hot water through the HDPE heaters. An agitator was used to improve the mixing process and to insure a uniform temperature through the tank.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of set up rig of the tank with the agitator

Description of the Tank System

The tank system consisted of a cylindrical tank made of polypropylene, PP, had a flat bottom and a free top surface with inside diameter of 1.53 m, and the depth of the fluid was 1.03 m, which was filled with 1880 liters of cold water. The agitator used in this system was an axial three-blade angular off-set impeller with a diameter of 0.5 m, and its shaft was fitted at an off-centre angle to the tank to achieve good top-to-bottom flow and to eliminate swirling. The pitch of the three blades was 45° . The agitator was positioned at 15° from the vertical wall of the tank. The agitator was driven by a three-phase electric motor with an output of 0.55 KW.

HDPE Heaters Type Radiator

The dimension and the geometries of the heaters used in this research as heat transfer surfaces were taken from the research report carried out by R. Aguilar Osorio and Keith Cliffe [16], which were estimated using the standard of the Tubular Exchanger Manufacturers Association (TEMA) and several research like Bell Taborek, and Donald Q. Kern, according to the operating conditions of the flow rate and the size of the tank. The heaters can be affected by the water inlet and outlet connection position and the type of the heater. Generally, the tubes arrangements of the tubular heaters are in-line and staggered. In this research was analyzed the thermal behavior of the heaters using both the in-line and staggered arrangements and different inlet and outlet to observe the effect of these arrangements.

The heaters were radiator types constructed with plain tubes. Four heaters with vertical tube bundles were used in the present study as heat transfer surfaces. These also provided a baffling effect for the side flow in the tank and this enhanced the heat transfer. The fluid circulated through the bundle of tubes of the heaters and a rotary motion was generated by the agitator as well as turbulence and the off-set agitator eliminated the need of additional baffles. In addition, the vertical tubes prevented swirl formation and caused both vertical and radial fluid flows, which were desired for good mixing and heating [17].

The heaters were constructed of high-density polyethylene, HDPE. The arrangement was single pass. One of them consisted of 3 rows with 50 vertical tubes in in-line arrangement, the transverse pitch, S_T , was 20 mm and the longitudinal pitch, S_L was 20 mm. The other three heaters consisted of 3 rows of 50, 51 and 51 vertical tubes in a staggered arrangement with transverse pitch was 40 mm and the longitudinal pitch, S_L was 10 mm. The tubes were fixed with the tube ends to the HDPE heaters. The heaters were located 0.3 m from the perimeter of the tank. Table 1 illustrates the characteristics of the heaters.

The mean feature of the HDPE heaters was the thin wall of the tubes which was 0.5 mm. The thermal conductivity of the HDPE is very low between 0.43 – 0.52 W/mK [18], which makes them necessary to use very thin walled of tubes in order to reduce the adverse effect on the heat transfer performance. One of the main

problems of using thin walled tube is that only low pressures can be used on the tube side, in this case, the limit was up to 1.7 bar.

Table 1. Characteristics of the heaters

Parameters		Heater (in-line)	Heater (staggered)
Tube outside diameter	d_o , [m]	0.01	0.01
Transverse pitch	S_T , [m]	0.02	0.04
Longitudinal pitch	S_L , [m]	0.02	0.02
Number of tube rows	N_{tr}	3	3
Number of tubes per row	N_t	50	51, 50, 51
Number of passes	N_p	1	1
Tube length	L_t , [m]	0.65	0.65
Head length	L_h , [m]	1.052	1.052
Heat wide	L_w , [m]	0.062	0.062
Heat deep	L_d , [m]	0.062	0.062
Heat transfer area	A [m ²]	3.02	3.06

Experimental Procedure

The technique and the procedure, for this investigation, were the same in all the tests. The tests were repeated 8 times for each case to obtain sufficient data to compare the results of the heat transfer coefficient in the agitated tank using the heaters with in-line and staggered arrangements.

To investigate the performance of this system several tests were designed as follows: The system was operated at 45, 60 and 100 rpm, the flow rates through the heater were 2000, 3000, 4000 l/h, the experiments were run with an initial temperature of approximately 22°C and a final temperature of 40°C on the tank side, and the temperature in the tube side was 54°C. Temperatures were recorded at the inlet and outlet of the heaters and in the water tank in four different zones. The temperatures in both sides were recorded every 5 minutes for each run with different flow rates, when the temperature was nearly to 40°C on the tank the temperature was recorded every one minute.

The heaters were equipped with a temperature recorder linked to two nickel-chromium/nickel-aluminium (type K) thermocouples, which were fitted at the inlet and outlet nozzles of the heater. The temperature of the water in the tank was measured with digital thermometers. The temperature measurements were accurate within $\pm 0.01^\circ\text{C}$. The flow rate on the heater was measured using a rotameter. The heaters were tested for both upward and downward flows to analyse the influence of the inlet and outlet on the system, including four cases. The inlets and outlets fixed for this investigation are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the heaters with different inlet and outlet

- Case 1. Inlet at the bottom left hand side and the outlet at the top right hand side (staggered).
- Case 2. Inlet at the bottom right hand side and the outlet to the top right hand side (staggered).
- Case 3. Inlet at the top right hand side and the outlet at the bottom left hand side (staggered).
- Case 4. Inlet at the top right hand side and the outlet at the bottom left hand side (in-line).

Leakage is a problem in plastic heat exchangers because it is difficult to seal de components. To check leaks in the HPDE heaters a red dye was injected on the tube side during the runs. The properties of the water in the tank side and in the tube side are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Physical properties of the hot and cold water [19,20, 21]

Physical properties of the water				
Parameter			Hot water	Cold water water
Density,	[kg/m ³]	ρ	988.03	995.65
Viscosity,	[Ns/m ²]	μ	0.000465	0.000798
Heat capacity,	[J/kg K]	C_p	4180.6	4178.4
Thermal conductivity, [W/m K]		k	0.06435	0.6154

Experimental Calculations

The heat transfer coefficient inside of the tubes of the heaters, h_i , was calculated by [22]:

$$Nu = \frac{h_i d_i}{k_t} = 0.026 Re^{0.8} Pr^{0.3} \quad (1)$$

Were Nu : is the Nusselt number, d_i : is the inside tube diameter, k : is the thermal conductivity, Re : is the Reynolds number, and Pr : is the Prandtl number.

The Reynolds number on the tube side was estimated using the next equation:

$$Re = \frac{\rho u d_i}{\mu} \quad (2)$$

Where ρ : is the density of the water, u : is the flow Velocity on the tube side, d_i : is the inside tube diameter, and μ : is the kinematic viscosity of the water.

The velocity was determined by:

$$u = \frac{\dot{V}}{A_p} \quad (3)$$

\dot{V} : is the volumetric flow rate in the tube side, A_p : is the one pass area. The one pass area, A_p , was obtained by:

$$A_p = \frac{\pi d_i^2}{4} \left(\frac{N_t}{N_p} \right) \quad (4)$$

d_i : is the inside tube diameter, N_t : number of tubes per row, N_p : number of passes

The overall heat transfer coefficient from the experiments was determined as follows:

The heat flow, Q , [23], between the hot water and tube wall was calculated by means of the inlet temperature, T_1 , and outlet temperature, T_2 , the mass flow rates measured, \dot{M} , and the heat capacity, C_p , as follows:

$$Q = \dot{M} C_p (T_1 - T_2) \quad (5)$$

Heat transfer in agitated tanks is an industrial operation whose performance depends on the characteristics of the agitator and the heat transfer surface. To predict the heat transfer rates in agitated tanks the following factors must be considered, the geometry of the system, type of agitator, the physical properties of the fluid and the transfer area. Process heat transfer in agitated tanks depends on a temperature difference between the heat transfer fluid and the process fluid, ΔT , the heat transfer area, A , and the overall heat transfer coefficient, U . This relationship represents the known heat transfer equation:

$$Q = UA\Delta T \quad (6)$$

This equation was applied when the tank and the heat transfer surface are operated continuously under constant conditions.

In this mixing and heating process the operation was batch and its solution involves unsteady state so the overall heat transfer coefficient is determined from the initial and final temperatures and the time taken to heat the water in the tank.

The heating time to raise the temperature from approximately 22 to 40°C on the tank side was recorded during the experimental runs, which are shown in Table 3.

If the heat transferred is dQ in time dt , then:

$$\frac{dQ}{dt} = \dot{M} C_p \frac{dT}{dt} \quad (7)$$

dT/dt : is the rate of change of temperature of the batch with time. \dot{M} : is the mass of the water in the tank, C_p : heat capacity

From a heat balance over the tank in an amount of time dt :

$$\dot{M} C_p \frac{dT}{dt} = UA\Delta T \quad (8)$$

If the water temperature in the heater is assumed, T_{heater} then;

$$\int \frac{dT}{(T_{heater} - T)} = \frac{UA}{\dot{M} C_p} \int dt$$

Integrating:

$$\ln\left(\frac{T_{heater} - T_1}{T_{heater} - T_2}\right) = \frac{UA}{\dot{M} C_p} t$$

Therefore, U is expressed by:

$$U = \frac{\dot{M} C_p}{At} \ln\left(\frac{T_{heater} - T_1}{T_{heater} - T_2}\right) \quad (9)$$

The transfer coefficient at the external tube bundle of the heater (on the tank side), h_o , was calculated by,

$$\frac{1}{h_o} = \frac{1}{U} - \frac{1}{h_i} - \frac{\delta}{K_t} \quad (10)$$

Where δ : is the thickness of the tubes with 0.4 mm and K_t : is the thermal conductivity of the HDPE of 0.52 W/mK [17].

It was assumed that fouling was negligible. This is because, the smooth surface of HDPE, have low fouling factors.

The Reynolds number on the tank side was predicted using the next expression [24]:

$$Re = \frac{NDa^2 \rho}{\mu} \quad (11)$$

Where N : is the agitator rotational speed, D_a : is the impeller diameter.

Results and Discussion

Table 3 shows the experimental results of the agitated tank fitted with heaters with in-line and staggered tube bundle arrangements using a flow rate of 2000, 3000 and 4000 l/h at 100 rpm in the tank. Different inlets and outlets were investigated for each case. The results for all the arrangements showed that the heat transfer coefficient increased with flow rate. This is thought to be consequence of increase turbulent within the tube arrangements as indicated by the increased Reynolds number.

From the testes it was observed that the best distribution of the fluid of the heaters was obtained with inlet at the top right-hand side and the outlet at the bottom left hand side. According to this finding, this position of the inlet and outlet was used for the heater with inline arrangement. Due to this, a comparison of the thermal behaviour was made of the heaters with in-line and staggered arrangements using the inlet at the top right-hand side and the outlet at the bottom left hand side, using the flow rate of 4000 l/h (case3 and case 4).

From the experimental results, show in Table 3, it can be observed a good agreement of the heat transfer coefficient in the tank side using three heaters with staggered tube bundles (cases 1 and 3). Case 2 showed a more variability of the heat transfer coefficient. At higher flow rate of 4000 l/h the heat transfer coefficient was approximately 34% higher than de other two cases. However, the inverse was demonstrated at lower flow rate. This is because at lower flow rate, pressure is less effective in driving water through the entire tube bundle and hence, the more remote tubes (those to the left-hand side of the heater) are bypassed. This suggests that the entrances and the outlets of the fluid in the heaters affect the thermal performance of the agitated tank in case 2 at lower flow rate.

While the heat transfer coefficient using a heater with in-line tube bundle (case 4), showed a greater heat transfer coefficient than the case 1 and case 3. This is because as the fluid circulates through the tube bundle, in-line tube bundle involved flow contraction and flow expansion by the bifurcation of the fluid due of the direction of flow impacting on the tubes, as it can be seen in Fig. 3, and hence, the area around the tube bundle was highly turbulence and higher heat transfer was obtained. Therefore, the overall heat transfer coefficient was greater from 14% to 23%.

The results of the heat transfer coefficient on the tank side using the overall heat transfer coefficient obtained with the heater with in-line tube bundle was greater from 34% to 52% in comparison with staggered tube bundle (case 1 and case 3), which provided a strong bypass stream between the tubes, the pressure was less effective in driving water along the tube bundle and hence the heating time was greater. The heating time was reduced in comparison of the staggered tube bundle. The heating time and power consumption were very important parameters on the heating performance.

Fig. 3. Tube bundle arrangements: a) in-line and b) staggered

Table 3. Results of the agitated tank fitted with heaters in staggered an in-line tube bundle

Flow rate l/h	Re (tube)	Re(tank)	Heating Time, Sec	U W/m ² K	h _i W/m ² K	h _o W/m ² K
Case 1. Staggered- inlet at the bottom left-hand side and the outlet to the top right hand side						
2000	1094	499468	8443	255.0	700	663
3000	1641	499468	7425	290.0	968	698
4000	2188	499468	6771	318.0	1219	745
Case 2. Staggered- inlet at the bottom right hand side and the outlet to the top right hand side						
2000	1094	499468	10253	210.0	700	427
3000	1641	499468	7146	301.3	968	766
4000	2188	499468	6389	337.0	1219	856
Case 3. Staggered- inlet at the top right hand side and the outlet to the bottom left hand side						
2000	1094	499468	8544	252.0	700.0	641
3000	1641	499468	7526	286.1	968.0	675
4000	2188	499468	6946	310.0	1219.0	700
Case 4. In-line - inlet at the top right hand side and the outlet at the bottom left hand side						
2000	1109	499468	7374	292.0	707.0	971
3000	1663	499468	6065	355.0	978.0	1228
4000	2217	499468	5329	404.0	1232.0	1470

From the results, it can be observed that the best result of the heat transfer coefficient in the agitated tank was obtained using the heater with in-line tube bundle with 4000 l/h flow rate in the tube side at 100 rpm on the tank side, which is 52% highest than staggered tube bundle.

Fig. 4 shows the behaviour of the heat transfer coefficient as a function of the flow rate of the four heaters, using a range of flow rate of 2000, 3000 and 4000 l/h at 100 rpm. From the plot can be observed a higher heat transfer performance on the tank side fixed with the in-line arrangement, which is considerably higher of those three staggered arrangements, which is due to the fluid impinging on the tube at an angle.

Due to the advantages in heat transfer performance for the in-line tube bundle, the heater with this tube bundle is the most suitable for the agitated tank analysed in this research. In both heater designs, the experimental data shows that the heat transfer coefficient increased with the flow rates. This was as consequence of increasing turbulence of the tube bundles.

Fig. 4. Flow rate as a function of the heat transfer coefficient for staggered and in-line arrangements

Injection dye into the tube side showed that no leakage occurred in this investigation from the heater to the tank. This problem was overcome by sealing very carefully the components of the heaters, a HPDE leak-proof seal was formed around them to ensure no leakage occurred.

The heaters were investigated for eight months, during this time it was observed a good corrosion resistance and no formation of deposit was presented. This is because, HDPE exhibits a good machinability, as a consequence a very smooth surface was attained, due to this the tubes allowed a slight possibility of formation of deposits.

The objective of mixing is homogenization, which reduces concentration and temperature gradients within the agitated system. From this investigation it was observed that mixing depends on the velocity of the flow, the viscosity of the fluid, and the geometrical arrangement of the space through which the fluid passes. The mixing process has a wide range of applications in the food, pharmaceutical, and paper industries, electrolysis, heating and cooling, heterogeneous chemical reaction, and others.

Future work

To extend the flow rate to investigate all the potential of the agitated system. To measure the temperature between tube passes to validate the heat transfer coefficient for each tube pass and compare with the theoretical predictions. To measure the velocity of the flow rate on the tube side to validate the theoretical prediction.

Conclusion

The thermal performance of an agitated tank was investigated using heaters with in-line and staggered tube bundle arrangements as heat transfer surfaces, and it was found that with the in-line tube bundle was obtained the best heat transfer coefficient with a flow rate of 4000 l/h at 100 rpm on the tank side, which was approximately 52% higher than the staggered arrangement. Therefore, the heater with in-line tube bundle was more suitable for the agitated tank analysed in this research. Injection of dye into the tube side showed that no leakage occurred from the heater to the tank. This problem was overcome by sealing very carefully the components of the heaters. The heaters were investigated for eight months, during this time it was observed a good corrosion resistance and no formation of deposit was presented. From this research it was observed that HDPE and PP materials are a potential alternative to construct heaters for mixing and heating processes, instead of metal alloys, due to the numerous advantages, for processes at low temperature and low pressure. They have lower cost, higher corrosion resistance, low fouling, and lighter weight.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank to the Instituto Politécnico Nacional of Mexico for the support received for this project.

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